

Hosios Loukas

also known as “Μονή Όσιου Λουκά”

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Entry tags: Religious Group, Religious Place, Monastery, Orthodoxy, Greece, Orthodoxy, Boeotia, Cenobitic Monastery

The monastery of Hosios Loukas is located on the slopes of Helicon, near the village of Steiris. The monastery is named after its eponymous saint, St. Luke of Steiris, a local holy man active in Boeotia in the early tenth century. Luke's activities are recorded in an anonymously authored vita that details the life of the saint up until his death in 953. The art and architecture of the monastery firmly places it as one of the crowning achievements of Middle Byzantine design. Widely known for its twin katholika, the monastery's construction is seen as a foundational moment in Byzantine architectural design in Greece. The older of the twin katholika is dedicated to the Theotokos and is the first example of a four-column cross-in-square church on mainland Greece; meanwhile, the current katholikon dedicated to Hosios Loukas is the progenitor of the domed-octagon type of church construction that forms the basis for the so-called 'Helladic' school of architecture. Inside, the Hosios Loukas church is adorned with an exquisite program of gold mosaics that depict the life of Jesus Christ, while the crypt of the monastery is also outfitted with an extensive cycle of paintings. The site continues to be a functioning monastery and is listed as a UNESCO World Heritage site.

Date Range: 953 CE - 1204 CE

Region: Hosios Loukas

Region tags: Greece, Boeotia

On the slopes of Mount Helicon, near the village of Steiris.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

General Variables

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Bouras, Ch. 2018. *The Architecture of the Monastery of Hosios Loukas*. Athens: Melissa.
- Source 2: Chatzidakis, N. 1997. *Hosios Loukas: Byzantine Art in Greece*. Athens: Melissa.
- Source 3: Connor, C.L. 1992. "Hosios Loukas as a Victory Church." *Greek, Roman, and Byzantine Studies* 33: 293–308.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://tib.oeaw.ac.at/static/reader/TIB/tib1.html#page/205/mode/2up>

– Source 1 Description: TIB entry for Hosios Loukas

– Source 1 URL: <https://whc.unesco.org/en/list/537/>

– Source 1 Description: UNESCO Site Designation

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:

– Year range: 1881-present

Notes: ongoing restoration works by the Greek Ministry of Culture

↳ Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Restoration works by the Greek Ministry of Culture

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

– Water source

Notes: The monastery is well-known for its association with Mount Helicon, as well as a sacred spring said to have been brought forth by the saint, Hosios Loukas.

↳ Type of elevation

– Mountain

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

– Leveling of ground

– Terracing

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– No

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– Yes

↳ Are there settlements in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

↳ Are there routes of travel in close proximity to the place:

– Yes

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– No

↳ One single feature

– Other [specify]: A large cistern lays below the monastery, as well as a crypt dug into the rock bed.

↳ A group of structures:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– No

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– Yes

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

– Healing

– Memorial

– Political

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– No

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: Dedicated to a local saint, Hosios Loukas.

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: One of the churches on-site is also dedicated to the Theotokos (Virgin Mary).

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– Yes

↳ Is it a cenotaph:

– No

↳ Does it commemorate a family/clan/group:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: It's possibly related to local, powerful families, however, the general consensus is not clear on who exactly.

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Imperial involvement is likely, but the extent to which is the source of much debate.

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Yes

↳ Groups:

– Priests

– Men

– Specialized labourers/craftspeople

– Other [specify]: Followers of Hosios Loukas the person and possibly funded by local elites.

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– No

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Yes

↳ Specify

– Other [specify]: The monastery is built on the site of Hosios Loukas' miracles, as well as the place of his death.

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Yes

↳ Is this sponsor of the same religious group/tradition as the main usage of the place:

– No

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: The likely sponsor likely wished for commemoration as well as using the place as an expression of power.

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– Field doesn't know

Design and Material Remains

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:

– Yes

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Percentage: 75

Notes: Percentage reflects the presence of two katholika (abbey churches) as well as a stone trapeza (refectory) and various other buildings within a walled compound.

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– I don't know

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– No

↳ Sand
– No

↳ Clay
– No

↳ Plaster
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Wood
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Grass
– No

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: N/A

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration part of the building (permanent):

– Yes

↳ On the outside:

– Yes

↳ On the inside:

– Yes

↳ Is decoration attached to the building, i.e. movable reliefs or tapestries

– Yes

Notes: Pseudo-kufic carvings directly on the buildings' exteriors, as well as various moveable icons hung on the walls within the churches.

↳ Is the decoration figural:

A figural representation is defined here as one that contains the depiction of discernible human, anthropomorphic, animal, or zoomorphic forms. In general, it differentiates between animate and inanimate beings, as well as between narrative compositions and still life, landscapes, abstraction, etc. Answer [Yes] for each type of figure depicted

– Yes

↳ Are there gods depicted:

– No

↳ Are there other supernatural beings depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there humans depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animals depicted:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal-human hybrids depicted:

– No

↳ Is the decoration non-figural:

– Yes

↳ Is it geometric/abstract

– Yes

↳ Floral motifs

– Yes

↳ Is it writing/caligraphy

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Is the decoration hidden or restricted from view:

– No

↳ Are there statues present:

– No

↳ Are there reliefs present:

A relief as opposed to sculpture carved on the round is a work of sculpture in which the figures project from a background support, generally a flat surface. Reliefs can be carved out of stone, clay, or a similar material.

– No

↳ Are there paintings present:

– Yes

↳ Are they panel paintings [movable]:

– Yes

↳ Are they wall paintings:

– Yes

↳ Type

– 'True' fresco

↳ Paintings representing the gods worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Paintings representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Paintings representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

– Other [specify]: Biblical narratives; saints; local abbots; apostles; angels

↳ Are there mosaics present:

– Yes

↳ Mosaics representing the god(s) worshipped at the place:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing mythological narratives:

– No

↳ Mosaics representing human/historical narratives:

– Yes

↳ Abstract mosaics:

– No

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

↳ Are there inscriptions as part of the decoration:

– No

↳ Other type of decoration:

– Yes [specify]: Cloisonné brickwork.

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic)

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract)

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife

– No

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols)

– Yes

↳ Humans

– No

↳ Supernatural narratives

– Yes

↳ Human narratives

– Yes

↳ Other [Specify]

–Other [specify]: N/A

Beliefs and Practices

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– Yes

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– No

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– No

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– No

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Yes

Do visitors communicate with gods:

– No

Do visitors communicate with other supernatural beings:

– Yes

Ritual and Performance

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– No

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Are material offerings present:

– No

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

By all the community

– Yes

By specific individuals

– Field doesn't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Is it required:

– Yes

Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– No

Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Yes

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

↳ How strict is pilgrimage:

– optional (common)

↳ Are pilgrimages the main reason for construction/establishment of the place:

– Yes

↳ Are pilgrimages to this place associated with significant life events:

– Yes

↳ Birth

– No

↳ Transition to adulthood

– No

↳ Death

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Pilgrimage to venerate the saint; for healing; for divine intervention; prophecy

↳ Does pilgrimage to this place involve following established routes (roads):

– Yes

- ↳ Are these routes maintained together with the place:
 - No

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Yes

- ↳ Is feasting connected to the worship/sacrifices performed at this place:
 - Yes

- ↳ Is feasting sponsored by the same entity that built/maintains the place:
 - Yes

- ↳ Priests
 - Yes

- ↳ Local elites
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Private contributions
 - Field doesn't know

- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: the monastic community; monks

- ↳ Does feasting occur in a specific location within the place:
 - Yes [specify]: Trapeza (refectory)

Are festivals present:

– Yes

- ↳ Frequency of festivals
 - specify: Annually (presumably) on the saint's feast day.

- ↳ Do all members of the society participate in the festival(s):
 - All members

- ↳ Are festivals a defining element in the construction/decoration of the place:
 - No
- ↳ On average, how many participants gather at this place:
 - number: Unknown
- ↳ Is feasting part of the festival(s):
 - Yes
- ↳ Is food consumption limited to certain members of the population:
 - Elites
 - Non-elites
 - Religious professionals

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– Yes

- ↳ Divination by examination of the exta:
Animals remains, internal organs, answer this question and subsequent question once for each species
 - No
- ↳ Divination through human communication:
 - No
- ↳ Divination through animal-behavior:
 - No
- ↳ Divination through non-living material:
 - Other [specify in comments]
- ↳ Other
 - Other [specify]: The saint himself was known for his prophecies.

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Yes

↳ Incubation

– Yes

↳ Healing magic

– No

↳ Cleansing

– No

↳ Offerings of models of body parts:

– No

↳ Expiation

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: N/A

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Yes

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

–specify: Unknown number

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

–specify: Unknown, but the monks would have performed several daily

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Yes

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Yes

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Yes

Notes: Wine.

Institutions and Scriptures

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

↳ Present full time

– Yes

↳ Present part time

– No

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Yes

Notes: Male monks

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Yes

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Yes

↳ Is access within the space segregated by this hierarchy:

– Yes

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Yes

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Yes

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present permanently:

– Yes

↳ Is a bureaucracy present on a temporary or seasonal basis:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Yes

↳ Is this control the primary supporting income of this place:

– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out land:
– Yes

↳ Does this place lease out tools:
– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Yes

↳ Public food distribution and/or storage:
– Yes

↳ Place for civic functions (census, elections, others):
– Yes
Notes: Tax collection

↳ Place for the practice of justice (trials, executions, etc.):
– No

↳ Function for water management:
– No

↳ Part of the transportation network:
– No

↳ Other
– Other [specify]: N/A

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Field doesn't know

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

↳ Are they written at this place:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they oral:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin and/or construction of this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there religious specialists in charge of interpreting the scriptures:

– Yes

↳ Are the scriptures part of the building/place:

– No

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Hosios Loukas, Oikonomides, Nicolas. "The First Century of the Monastery of Hosios Loukas" 46 (1992). <https://doi.org/10.2307/1291657>.

Reference: Hosios Loukas, "Art and Miracles in Medieval Byzantium: The Crypt at Hosios Loukas and Its Frescoes" 29, no. 05 (January 1, 1992). <https://doi.org/10.5860/choice.29-2506>.

Reference: Hosios Loukas, Bouras, Ch.. The Architecture of the Monastery of Hosios Loukas. Athens: Melissa, 2018.